

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Abduganieva Gulzoda Karimullaevna

**INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE OF CCOUNTING AND THE PRACTICAL
SITUATION IN UZBEKISTAN**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

2023/IYUN

★ ★ ★ ★ ★
HONORED
MENTION
★ ★ ★ ★ ★

YOUR
SEAL